

Fig 2H AGS

Fig 2H

Fig 4J AGS

Fig 4J MKN-45

Fig 5E

Fig 5F

Fig 5H AGS

Fig 5H MKN-45

Fig 6C AGS

Fig 6D MKN-45

Fig 6E AGS

inhibitor NC	+	-	-	-
miR-148b-5p inhibitor	-	+	+	+
pcDNA	-	-	+	-
pcDNA-CYR61	-	-	-	+

+	-	-	-
-	+	+	+
-	-	+	-
-	-	-	+

+	-	-	-
-	+	+	+
-	-	+	-
-	-	-	+

CYR61

42kd

GAPDH

36kd

Fig 6E MKN-45

inhibitor NC	+	-	-	-
miR-148b-5p inhibitor	-	+	+	+
pcDNA	-	-	+	-
pcDNA-CYR61	-	-	-	+

+	-	-	-
-	+	+	+
-	-	+	-
-	-	-	+

+	-	-	-
-	+	+	+
-	-	+	-
-	-	-	+

CYR61

42kd

GAPDH

36kd

Fig 6L AGS

inhibitor NC	+	-	-	-
miR-148b-5p inhibitor	-	+	+	+
Si-NC	-	-	+	-
Si-CYR61	-	-	-	+

	+	-	-	-
	-	+	+	+
	-	-	+	-
	-	-	-	+

	+	-	-	-
	-	+	+	+
	-	-	+	-
	-	-	-	+

E-cadherin

105kd

Vimentin

53kd

GAPDH

36kd

Fig 6L MKN-45

mimic NC	+	-	-	-
miR-148b-5p mimic	-	+	+	+
pcDNA	-	-	+	-
pcDNA-CYR61	-	-	-	+

	+	-	-	-
	-	+	+	+
	-	-	+	-
	-	-	-	+

	+	-	-	-
	-	+	+	+
	-	-	+	-
	-	-	-	+

E-cadherin

105kd

Vimentin

53kd

GAPDH

36kd

